

THE MAIN ISSUES OF USING NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING

*R. Bolieva*¹

Abstract:

Today we can talk about intensifying the process of using Internet technologies in modern education. This process poses a number of pressing problems that are the subject of discussion by scientists, teachers, and educators who link the development of universities with the active use of Internet technologies and the creation of a unified information educational space that promotes the development and self-realization of students. This thesis discusses about issues which can be seen in teaching in the modern universities.

Key words: educational activity, lesson, question, answer, lecture, assignment, seminar.

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In the last few years, in the speeches and publications of Uzbek philosophers, sociologists, psychologists and teachers, as well as scientists, writers, politicians and other representatives of the domestic intelligentsia, the problem of education has shown particular relevance. This can hardly be considered a mere accident or a new intellectual fashion: rather, behind this there are some new trends in the global civilizational process. At the same time, special attention in any discussions on the topic of education is paid to both a rather harsh critical assessment of classical educational paradigms, concepts, models, institutions, and the search for their new images, more adequate to the modern cultural situation [1].

The traditional model of education known to us almost always represents a simple translation of culture, and, as a rule, of some mono-culture dominant in a given society and state at a certain time. The main meaning of such education is usually training, understood as the simple assimilation by students of a certain amount of knowledge accumulated by humanity in various fields, and, to a large extent, scattered knowledge, with the aim of preparing a specialist who is ready to join existing socio-economic institutions and complexes [2].

At the same time, it is believed that it is possible and sufficient to simply transfer into the consciousness of those “forming” specially selected and appropriately processed cultural material, and all this diversity and vastness, at best, are only an insignificant background in the preparation of a “professional” [3]. Of course, in such education = training, a person is not only not a subject of the educational process, but is generally absent as a person, an individual; he is just an object of learning here. As is known, traditional forms of educational activity: lesson, question, answer; lecture, assignment, seminar. In this regard, it is authoritarian and totalitarian both in content and in form, and the authoritarian content of education is a key point that predetermines everything else in educational systems and complexes. There is no attitude towards personal self-determination, the search for images

¹ *Bolieva Rokhila Khairullayevna, teacher, Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction, Uzbekistan*

of oneself, one's ways of thinking and feeling, one's life in this world. In other words, such education=training is not education at all in the proper sense of the word, understood as the process of becoming a person [4].

The modern cultural situation decisively requires a significant revision of traditional educational paradigms, which today turn out to be untenable in the sense of ensuring the development of any civilized society. Even at the beginning of the 20th century, F. Nietzsche, Z. Freud, O. Spengler and a number of other outstanding thinkers clearly declared the exceptional hostility of European culture to man and the inevitability of its crushing collapse, which was later exhaustively confirmed by many events of this century.

Already now, the world as a whole is becoming multipolar and multicultural, and the leading trends in modern education are its humanization and humanitarization [5], dialogism and project-based approach. In this regard, there is already an understanding that education and training are very different things, and that education should not be just a broadcast.

However, today educational methodologies and technologies are changing, even the content of educational programs and curricula, but not the very essence of education, which so far remains completely unchanged, since the main mental change in this context has not yet occurred. There is still no understanding that education should not simply transmit culture, and especially not any kind of mono-culture [6]. The broadcast of a culture that has revealed its hostility and repressiveness towards people, a culture that is collapsing, can hardly be considered reasonable at all. This means that the meanings, goals and values of education must change.

At the moment, in modern society there is an unstoppable development of information technology, especially in the field of multimedia, virtual reality and global networks [7]. The use of these technologies in various spheres of human activity has given rise to many philosophical, theoretical, methodological and socio-economic problems. The phenomenon of the global computer network Internet causes the greatest public resonance. The Internet is a convenient source of various information, which qualitatively changes the entire system of accumulation, storage, distribution and use of collective human experience.

Internet technologies, apparently, should be understood as various types of services provided to the user of the global network: e-mail and mailing lists, WWW service, chat conversation, html forums, guest books, ICQ, teleconferences, news servers, ftp servers and other types of services. Or should Internet technologies be understood as ActiveX technologies: Internet Explorer browser, FrontPage 97 web page editor, Office 97 web-compatible package, VBScript, JavaScript and others programming languages? One way or another, by Internet technologies we can understand the totality of software products and Internet technologies and various types of services [8]. Mastering the Internet is mastering a new information environment with specific means of activity in it. These tools allow not only to quickly obtain information, but also develop thinking, give a person the opportunity to solve creative problems in a new way, and change the existing style of mental activity.

The Internet, being an achievement of the 20th century, undoubtedly determines the success of informatization of society in the 21st century. However, today there is a gradual shift away from enthusiasm for the possibilities of the Internet to awareness and search for ways to solve various problems caused by the increasing use of telecommunications in various spheres of human activity. These issues range from ethical to environmental. This attitude towards the use of modern information technologies reflects a necessary and natural stage in the development of society. After all, "the main object exposed to the influence of information technology is a person. Technical and information means become a kind of extension of not only the human body, but also his mind. Expanding his

capabilities, a person becomes more and more unconsciously dependent on the artificial technological environment that he himself created [9].

What is a necessary condition for the comfortable existence of an individual in the information society? How to prepare a personality in all its aspects for harmonious development? Who should do this and how? Let's try to find answers to the questions posed. To ensure the success of solving problems arising in the process of informatization of society, it is necessary, in our opinion, to form and develop the information culture of the individual. The system of lifelong education is called upon to solve this problem, the various stages of which are also influenced by informatization. Of all social institutions, education is the basis of the socio-economic and spiritual development of any society [10].

Education determines the position of the state in the modern world and of the individual in society. If the informatization of education loses its humanitarian aspect, then society will inevitably run the risk of degradation of human relations and contacts as the basis of mutual understanding. The creation of fundamentally new technology did not make machines the main factor in social life, but only increased the role and importance of human factors themselves.

Technocratic trends in e-learning turn out to be incompatible with the main trend of modern education, which consists in the transition from a knowledge-based to a personal paradigm of the pedagogical process. Education at the present stage is faced with the task of developing methodology, methods and methods for combining information, demonstration and interactive capabilities of computer technologies, including the Internet, in order to achieve an educational and developmental effect in the development of personality.

Based on the current state of informatization of society, it is necessary to expand the already established understanding of the information culture of the individual. For the safe existence and harmonious development of members of society, information culture must reflect the following aspects: information ethics, aesthetics, ergonomics of information technology, information security, not only in the sense of protecting information, but also in the sense of protecting the human psyche.

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